

Outcome Expectations and Fibromyalgia: Perceived Benefits of Exercise Are Associated with Self-Efficacy and Physical Performance

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SESSION INFORMATION

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Session Type: ACR Poster Session A

Session Title: Fibromyalgia and Other Clinical Pain Syndromes Poster – ARHP

Session Time: 9:00AM-11:00AM

Background/Purpose:

Outcome expectancy is recognized as a determinant of exercise engagement and adherence. Higher outcome expectations for exercise (OEE) have been shown to correlate with greater motivation to exercise in patients with osteoarthritis. However, little is known about which factors may influence OEE in fibromyalgia. This is the first study to examine the associations between baseline OEE and demographic, physical and psychosocial variables in patients with fibromyalgia.

Methods:

This study is a cross-sectional, secondary analysis of data obtained at baseline evaluation from a single-center, 52-week, randomized comparative effectiveness trial of Tai Chi versus aerobic exercise for participants with fibromyalgia (n=226). Baseline measures included demographics, physical performance, outcome expectancy, self-efficacy, anxiety, depression, stress, social support, and pain coping. OEE was assessed with the 9-item Outcome Expectations for Exercise Scale, where a higher value indicates stronger expectation for a positive outcome. Independent t-test and chi-square test were used to determine the relationship between participant characteristics and high OEE (\geq median of 3.9). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

Participants had a mean age of 51.8 years and body mass index of 30.0 kg/m², 92.5% were female, 61.1% were white, and 36.0% possessed at least college-level education. Compared to the lower OEE group, individuals with a higher OEE were more likely to have a greater self-efficacy (5.7 \pm 2.2 vs. 4.8 \pm 2.0; P=0.001) and physical performance as assessed by 6-minute walk distance (meters) (423.8 \pm 85.8 vs. 382.2 \pm 77.6; P<0.001) or SF-36 physical component (31.8 \pm 7.0 vs. 29.6 \pm 8.0; P=0.029). There were no other significant associations.

Conclusion:

Our study found that higher OEE was significantly associated with greater self-efficacy and physical performance. Future longitudinal research should explore how these relationships affect long-term exercise engagement for patients with fibromyalgia.

Disclosure: **G. Chi**, None; **J. Marszalek**, None; **L. L. Price**, None; **R. R. Bannuru**, Fidia, 8; **C. Wang**, None.

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